

Numerical Analysis of Scale Effects on Resistance and Propulsion Performance of the K-SUPRAMAX in Low-Speed Condition

Jae-Hyeon An¹, Kwang-Jun Paik^{1,*}, Myeong-Min Kim¹, Seung-Hyun Hwang²

¹ Department of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering, Inha University, Incheon, South Korea

² Korea Research Institute of Ships & Ocean engineering(KRISO), Daejeon, South Korea

Abstract. In this study, numerical simulations at full-scale were conducted for the 66K DWT K-SUPRAMAX ship to perform a fundamental investigation on resistance and self-propulsion performance under low-speed conditions in calm water, taking scale effects into account. Based on the full-scale CFD analysis at a low speed of 4 knots, it was found that the residuary resistance coefficient decreases compared to the model-scale due to scale effects, thereby influencing the evaluation of full-scale resistance performance. The Propeller open water (POW) performance was found to be consistent with the ITTC-1978 extrapolation results. In the full-scale analysis, it was confirmed that there is no significant difference in POW performance between the design and low rotational speeds due to the fully turbulent flow. Accordingly, the self-propulsion performance at low speed was evaluated based on the design rotational speed. In addition, the wake fraction estimated using the ITTC-1978 method tends to overpredict the full-scale W_n as speed decreases. However, applying the W_{TS} extracted from full-scale self-propulsion CFD analysis improves the agreement with the actual full-scale W_n value. At low speeds, compared to the design speed, the effective wake fraction increases and the thrust deduction factor decreases, resulting in improved hull efficiency. Nevertheless, a reduction in propeller rotational speed leads to a decrease in open water efficiency

Keywords: Low speed, Full-scale, Scale effect, K-SUPRAMAX, Calm water, Resistance and Propulsion

1 Introduction

Due to the recent acceleration of global warming, efforts to regulate CO₂ emissions have been continuously pursued. The IMO (International Maritime Organization) introduced the EEDI (Energy Efficiency Design Index) to enhance the energy efficiency of ships and thereby reduce CO₂ emissions [1]. In line with this, environmental regulations have been strengthened through the promotion of high-efficiency shipbuilding and the implementation of operational guidelines aimed at improving navigational efficiency. High-efficiency shipbuilding includes the development of eco-friendly hull forms, high-performance propulsion systems, and energy recovery devices. Operational strategies, such as operating ships at a reduced speed of about 4 knots, have proven to be effective methods for lowering CO₂ emissions and fuel consumption [2], [3], [4]. Moreover, it offers the advantage of requiring no retrofitting of existing ships.

To meet the EEDI requirements, reducing ship speed has been adopted as an effective means of decreasing CO₂ emissions. Accordingly, accurate estimation of the required power has become increasingly important, and CFD-based self-propulsion simulations have emerged as a useful tool in this context. However, under low-speed conditions, unlike at the design speed, the decrease in η_O and the increase in W_{TS} may result in deviations in self-propulsion performance. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate changes in self-propulsion characteristics under low-speed conditions. In general, full-scale self-propulsion performance is estimated by applying the ITTC-1978 method to model-scale results. However, discrepancies may arise because the t and η_R do not account for scale effects. Thus, a fundamental study is required to evaluate the applicability of the ITTC method under low-speed conditions and to compare self-propulsion performance at design and low speeds, with the aim of improving the accuracy of full-scale self-propulsion predictions.

As a preceding study on full-scale self-propulsion estimation, Calm water resistance analyses were conducted for the KVLCC2 hull form at four different scales, and it was confirmed that both C_{VP} and C_R tend to decrease as the scale approaches full-scale [5]. Regarding changes in W_n , For the KVLCC2, the difference in W_n between model and full scales was analyzed, and wake contraction effects caused by increased Reynolds number were

* Correspondence to: kwangjun.paik@inha.ac.kr

confirmed [6]. Furthermore, studies observed that the inflow velocity increases at full-scale, and when comparing across various speeds, the inflow velocity decreases at lower speeds, leading to an increase in the W_n [7], [8]. In full-scale POW performance analysis, A comparative analysis of model-scale and full-scale results was conducted for the KP505 propeller. Their study showed that, compared to the model-scale, the influence of viscosity decreases at full-scale, resulting in an increase in the K_T and a decrease in the K_Q . They also confirmed that the full-scale POW performance remains consistent regardless of wall y^+ values [9]. For the full-scale self-propulsion performance analysis, simulations were conducted on the KCS hull form, and the self-propulsion factors between model and full scales were compared [10]. In a similar prior study, full-scale self-propulsion simulations were performed for a large crude oil tanker, and a comparative analysis was carried out between the self-propulsion factors derived from the ITTC-1978 method and those obtained through full-scale CFD analysis [11].

Research on performance evaluation under low-speed conditions remains relatively limited. In addition, the scale effect caused by the Reynolds number difference between model and full-scale leads to significant changes in flow characteristics, such as rapid pressure recovery near the stern and increased axial velocity into the propeller. As a result, it becomes challenging to accurately predict full-scale performance based on model test results using the Froude similarity law.

In this study, full-scale numerical simulations were conducted for the low-speed, K-SUPRAMAX ship to perform a fundamental investigation on resistance and self-propulsion performance under low-speed conditions in calm water, considering scale effects. The flow characteristics at both design and low speeds were analyzed, and the scale effects were evaluated by comparing the model-scale numerical results, full-scale performance estimated using the ITTC extrapolation method and directly computed resistance and self-propulsion performance at full-scale.

2 Numerical method

2.1 Target ship and propeller

The K-SUPRAMAX, a 66K bulk carrier designed by the KRISO, was selected as the target ship, with the KP1306 propeller chosen as the corresponding propulsion system. The geometry of the selected ship and propeller is presented in Figure 1, while their principal specifications are provided in Table 1 and Table 2 for the ship and propeller, respectively.

Figure 1. Target ship and propeller model geometry: (a) 66k DWT K-SUPRAMAX; (b) KP1306 propeller.

Table 1. Principal particulars of the target ship

Particulars	Unit	Full-scale	Model-scale
Scale ratio, λ	-	1	24
Length, L_{PP}	m	192	8
Length, L_{WL}	m	104.5	4.35
Breath, B	m	36	1.50
Draft, T	m	11.2	0.47
Displacement, ∇	m ³	65,028	4.704
Design speed, V	knots		14.5

Table 2. Principal particulars of the target propeller

Particulars	Unit	Full-scale	Model-scale
Scale ratio, λ	-	1	24
Diameter, D_p	m	6	0.25
rps, n	rps	2	17
Pitch ratio, P/D_p	-		0.727
Thickness of ratio, t/D_p	-		0.012
Chord ratio, c/D_p	-		0.266

2.2 Governing equation

The RANS (Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes) equations and the continuity equation were employed as governing equations to simulate three-dimensional incompressible viscous flow. This formulation, incorporating fluid viscosity, is expressed in Equations (1) and (2). The flow around the hull was assumed to be incompressible and inviscid, except at the hull surface.

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial \bar{x}_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial \bar{x}_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial \bar{x}_i} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \bar{x}_j^2} (\mu \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial \bar{x}_j} - \rho \bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j) \quad (2)$$

where ρ , ν , P , x_i , (x, y, z) and $u_i(u, v, w)$ correspond to the density of the fluid, kinematic viscosity, pressure, spatial coordinates, and velocity components along each coordinate axis, respectively. The Realizable k- ϵ turbulence model, which is widely used in resistance analysis and ship self-propulsion simulations, was employed to analyze the flow characteristics around the ship. This model effectively controls grid resolution near wall boundaries and provides relatively accurate numerical results, making it a preferred choice in the field of ship hydrodynamics. The SIMPLE algorithm was used to couple velocity and pressure, and the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method was applied to account for free-surface interactions induced by the movements of the propeller and rudder.

2.3 Computation domain and grid system

For the full-scale resistance and self-propulsion simulations, the full-domain mesh system shown in Figure 2(a) was employed. To more accurately capture the motion of the ship, an overset mesh was also applied. All boundaries were defined as velocity inlet. The number of computational cells was approximately 6.93M for the resistance analysis. In the case of the self-propulsion simulation, fine mesh refinement was applied in the stern region to match the mesh resolution in the propeller rotation zone, resulting in a total of approximately 9.12M cells. The boundary conditions used for the full-scale POW analysis are illustrated in Figure 2(b). The inlet was set as a velocity inlet, the outlet as a pressure outlet, and the side boundaries were defined as symmetry. For modeling the rotating region, the sliding mesh method was applied with a rotation angle increment of 2 degrees to ensure convergence. The total number of cells used in this setup was approximately 3.09M.

Figure 2. Computational domain & Boundary conditions: (a) Resistance and self-propulsion; (b) POW.

3 Validation of numerical simulation (Model-scale)

Prior to conducting the full-scale simulations, numerical validation was performed using the model ship. As part of the verification, a GCI test was carried out at the design speed, and the results are summarized in Table 3. Both resistance and motions (sinkage and trim) demonstrated grid convergence within 1%. In addition, resistance analyses were conducted at six different speeds, and as shown in Table 4, the numerical results exhibited good agreement with the KRISO experimental data, with errors in both resistance and motion remaining within 4%.

A simulation was conducted under low-speed conditions using the model ship. When comparing the flow fields at the design speed and low speed, it was clearly observed that the inflow velocity toward the stern significantly decreased under low-speed conditions (Figure 3(a)), resulting in a thicker boundary layer compared to that at the design speed (Figure 3(b)). Furthermore, analysis of the resistance coefficients at various speeds revealed that frictional resistance became the dominant component at lower speeds, leading to a decreasing trend in the difference between C_{TM} and C_{VM} (Figure 3(c)).

Table 3. GCI of resistance coefficients and motions in calm water at model scale ($Fr = 0.172$)

Case	Number of grids	C_{TM} ($\times 10^2$)	GCI ₂₁ (%)	Sinkage ($\sigma/L_{pp} \times 10^3$)	GCI ₂₁ (%)	Trim (deg)	GCI ₂₁ (%)
Coarse	1.93M	3.969		0.1460		0.1859	
Medium	3.84M	3.992	0.78	0.1470	0.88	0.1864	0.30
Fine	7.68M	4.007		0.1476		0.1867	

Table 4. Comparison of C_{TM} and ship motion at various speeds

Particulars	Velocity(knots)	$C_{TM} \cdot 10^3$	$\sigma/L_{pp} \cdot 10^2$	τ [deg]
EFD (KRISO)	10	3.975	0.0703	0.0830
	12	3.928	0.1023	0.1240
	14	3.969	0.1401	0.1750
	14.5	4.021	0.1513	0.1900
	15	4.105	0.1635	0.2060
	16	4.333	0.1875	0.2370
CFD (Present)	10	3.900 (1.89%)	0.0675 (1.80%)	0.0815 (3.99%)
	12	3.884 (1.10%)	0.0990 (1.32%)	0.1224 (3.23%)
	14	3.914 (1.38%)	0.1379 (1.80%)	0.1719 (1.61%)
	14.5	3.992 (0.73%)	0.1470 (1.88%)	0.1864 (2.82%)
	15	4.062 (1.04%)	0.1615 (1.29%)	0.2034 (1.25%)
	16	4.295 (0.88%)	0.1869 (1.33%)	0.2338 (0.31%)

Figure 3. Comparing the flow fields at the design speed and low speed: (a) Velocity vector; (b) Boundary thickness; (c) Variation of resistance components according to ship speed.

In the model ship self-propulsion analysis, the direct rotation method was applied. As shown in Table 5, the numerical results exhibited good agreement with the experimental self-propulsion factors at the design speed, with deviations within 5%.

The self-propulsion factors were analyzed under both the design and low-speed conditions. As illustrated in Figures 4(a) and 4(b), the stern C_p distribution shows that, under low-speed conditions, an increase in stern pressure results in a tendency for the W_{TM} to increase. Furthermore, the influence of propeller suction decreased at low speed, leading to a reduced low-pressure distribution around the propeller and a subsequent decrease in the t . Additionally, as the speed decreased, the advance coefficient was reduced, causing a drop in η_o . This, in turn, led to a decrease in η_D compared to that at design speed. These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the model-scale numerical simulation in evaluating self-propulsion performance under low-speed steady conditions.

Table 5. Comparison of self-propulsion factors for model-scale

	KRISO (EFD)	Present (CFD)	Present (CFD)
V _s (knots)		14.5	4
W_{TM}	0.437	0.418 (-4.3%)	0.468
W_{TS}		0.352	0.339
t	0.209	0.201 (-3.8%)	0.184
η_H		1.217	1.234
η_R	1.012	1.006 (-0.6%)	1.022
η_o		0.561	0.536
η_D		0.686	0.676

Figure 4. Stern C_p distribution of the model-scale at different ship speeds: (a) 14.5 knots; (b) 4.0 knots.

4 Results

4.1 Evaluation of full-scale resistance performance

Based on the validated numerical simulation of the model-scale, the mesh system was extended to the full-scale model. To verify the mesh convergence of the full-scale simulation, a Grid Convergence Index (GCI) test was conducted under the design speed condition. The GCI method was employed to quantitatively assess the degree of numerical convergence [12]. The convergence test was performed based on mesh resolution, with the mesh conditions for resistance analysis categorized as fine, medium, and coarse. As shown in Table 6, the GCI test results indicated that both resistance and motion exhibited convergence errors of less than 1%, confirming that the results were within acceptable limits. Therefore, the medium mesh was selected as the full-scale resistance mesh configuration for this study.

Table 6. GCI of resistance coefficients and motion in calm water at full scale ($Fr = 0.172$)

Case	Number of grids	C_{TS} ($\times 10^3$)	$GCI_{21}(\%)$	Sinkage ($\sigma/L_{pp} \times 10^3$)	$GCI_{21}(\%)$	Trim (deg)	$GCI_{21}(\%)$
Coarse	3.50M	2.521		0.1439		0.1970	
Medium	6.93M	2.536	0.5	0.1455	0.3	0.1972	0.2
Fine	13.7M	2.544		0.1460		0.1980	

A numerical resistance analysis was performed for the full-scale ship in calm water. As shown in Figure 5, the flow field exhibited a Kelvin wave pattern consistent with that observed in previous studies [13] (Figure 5(a)). When comparing the wave profiles based on medium mesh resolutions for both the model and full-scale ships, satisfactory agreement was observed (Figure 5(b)). As shown in Figure 6, the C_p distributions along the stern and sides of the hull also demonstrated similar trends.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Comparison of wave between the model and full-scale ship: (a) Wave elevation; (b) Wave profile.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Comparison of C_p between the model and full-scale ship: (a) Model-scale [13]; (b) Full-scale (Present).

To evaluate the scale effect at full-scale, the hull boundary layer distributions of the model and full-scale ships were compared. As shown in Figure 7, the boundary layer thickness was found to be reduced in full-scale case, which is attributed to the increased inflow velocity. As confirmed in Figure 7(c), the increased inflow velocity results in higher inflow values for the full-scale ship compared to the model-scale when examining the radial inflow velocity distribution on the wake plane. This led to wake contraction in the nominal wake field at full-scale, and the W_n increased from 0.533 on the model-scale to 0.353 in the full-scale, as shown in Figure 7(d). In the stern C_p distribution, the increased inflow velocity and reduced boundary layer thickness in the full-scale case resulted in a decrease in pressure loss at the stern (Figure 8). Consequently, the pressure difference between the bow and stern was reduced compared to the model ship, suggesting a potential reduction in viscous pressure resistance at full-scale.

Figure 7. Evaluation of scale effects between model and full-scale ships: (a) Boundary thickness of model; (b) Boundary thickness of full; (c) V_x/V According to wake radius; (d) Wake field.

Figure 8. Comparison of stern C_p distributions between the model and full-scale ship: (a) Model-scale; (b) Full-scale.

A full-scale resistance analysis was performed under calm water and low-speed conditions across six different ship speeds to examine the variation in resistance components. As shown in Figure 9, the analysis of the full-scale W_n revealed a slight increase in the low-velocity region beneath the hub as the ship speed decreased, while no significant difference was observed in the vortex region. As presented in Table 7, the W_n under low-speed conditions increased by approximately 9.3% compared to the design speed.

Figure 9. Comparison of full-scale wake fields at different ship speeds: (a) 14.5knots; (b) 10.0knots; (c) 7.0knots; (d) 4.0knots.

Table 7. Comparison of $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ at different ship speeds

V_s (knots)	$W_{n(Full-scale)}$
14.5	0.3532
10.0	0.3621
7.0	0.3711
4.0	0.3862

In addition, a comparison was made between the full-scale wake fraction obtained through CFD and that extrapolated from model-scale results. As shown in Equation (3), which is used for extrapolating the full-scale nominal wake fraction, $W_{n(Model-scale)}$ refers to the nominal wake fraction extracted from the model-scale resistance analysis, and W_{TM} represents the effective wake fraction obtained from the model-scale self-propulsion analysis. W_{TS} is the value estimated by applying the ITTC extrapolation method given in Equation (4). The t and W_{TM} were obtained from the model self-propulsion analysis. The form factor $(1+k)$, calculated as 1.218 using the Prohaska method during the model resistance analysis, was applied. In addition, the roughness allowance ΔC_F was determined using Equation (5). k_s was set to the ITTC-recommended value of 150E-06 [14]. Accordingly, a comparative analysis was conducted between the $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ values obtained from the full-scale resistance CFD and those calculated using Equation (3).

$$W_{n(Full-scale)} = W_{n(Model-scale)} \times \frac{W_{TS}}{W_{TM}} \quad (3)$$

$$W_{TS} = (t + 0.04) + (W_{TM} - t - 0.04) \frac{(1+k)C_{FS} + \Delta C_F}{(1+k)C_{FM}} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta C_F = 0.044 \left[\left(\frac{k_s}{L_{WL}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} - 10Re^{-\frac{1}{3}} \right] + 0.000125 \quad (5)$$

A comparison of $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ obtained from full-scale CFD and the extrapolation method shows that, at the design speed, discrepancies in $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ began to appear from $r/R=0.4$, as illustrated in Figure 10(a). In contrast, under low-speed conditions, significant differences emerged from $r/R=0.2$, as shown in Figure 10(b). This is attributed to the overestimation of W_{TS} in low-speed conditions, caused by the friction coefficient increase rate of C_{FM} being greater than that of C_{FS} when applying Equation (4). Furthermore, there is currently no established method for accurately extrapolating the position and size of the bilge vortex, one of the three-dimensional boundary layer separation phenomena observed at full-scale. This limitation makes it challenging to predict flow features accurately during scale-up. Therefore, it is considered more appropriate to compare $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ values using W_{TS} obtained directly from full-scale self-propulsion analyses at both design and low speeds.

Figure 10. Comparison of W_n from the model-scale, full-scale, and wake scaling method: (a) 14.5knots; (b) 4.0knots.

The 2D method was applied to analyze the resistance components across various ship speeds. While the total resistance and frictional resistance at full-scale decreased and the C_R remained similar, Figure 11 shows that pressure recovery at the stern in the full-scale case led to a reduction in both C_{VP} and C_R . Additionally, as shown in Figure 12, pressure loss at the stern slightly increased as the speed decreased, resulting in a smaller difference in C_R between the model and full-scale ships at low speeds. Consequently, full-scale C_R exhibited a decreasing trend across all speeds compared to the model-scale, confirming the validity of the full-scale numerical analysis under low-speed conditions.

Figure 11. Comparison of C_R between the model and full-scale ships.

Figure 12. Comparison of stern C_p distributions at different ship speeds: (a) 14.5knots; (b) 10.0knots; (c) 7.0knots; (d) 4.0knots.

4.2 Evaluation of full-scale POW performance

The full-scale POW numerical analysis was performed based on the design rotational speed of 2rps. As shown in Figure 13(a), when compared to the model-scale POW performance, the full-scale results exhibited an increase in K_T and a decrease in K_Q due to the relatively lower influence of viscosity at full-scale (Table 8). Additionally, a comparison between the full-scale POW performance and the extrapolated model-scale POW results using the ITTC method showed that, except for a high advance coefficient of 0.7, the differences across all other advance ratios were within approximately 5% (Table 9).

Furthermore, considering the Reynolds number variation due to different rotational speeds, POW performance was compared between the design rotational speed (2rps, $Rn: 4.42E+07$) and a low-speed condition (0.6rps, $Rn: 1.33E+07$). The low-speed rotational speed was estimated using the model-scale self-propulsion factors at each ship speed. As shown in Figure 13(b), the POW characteristics between the design and low-speed rotational speeds

were found to be similar. This similarity is attributed to the fully turbulent flow condition at full-scale, where Reynolds number effects are diminished, and thus the POW performance does not significantly change with rotational speed. Therefore, it was confirmed that applying the design rotational speed in the thrust identity method is acceptable for low-speed self-propulsion analyses.

Figure 13. Evaluation of full-scale POW performance: (a) Evaluation of full-scale POW performance based on the design rotation; (b) Comparison of full-scale POW performance at design and low rotation.

Table 8. Comparison of POW performance between model and full-scale (Model: 17rps, Full: 2rps)

J	K_T (%)	$10K_Q$ (%)	η_o (%)
0.3	+1.30	-1.84	+3.20
0.4	+1.08	-2.69	+3.87
0.5	+0.80	-3.91	+4.90
0.6	+0.53	-5.88	+6.81
0.7	+0.22	-9.79	+11.10

Table 9. Comparison between ITTC-extrapolated and full-scale POW performance

J	K_T (%)	$10K_Q$ (%)	η_o (%)
0.3	+1.18	-0.62	+1.80
0.4	+0.93	-1.28	+2.24
0.5	+0.60	-2.22	+2.89
0.6	+0.25	-3.71	+4.12
0.7	+0.32	-6.56	+6.68

4.3 Evaluation of full-scale self-propulsion performance

To evaluate full-scale self-propulsion performance under low-speed conditions, the sliding mesh technique was applied for simulation. As previously confirmed, there was a negligible difference in POW performance between the design and low rotational speeds. Therefore, the POW performance at the design rotational speed was used for both the design speed and low-speed conditions when applying the thrust identity method. Figure 14 shows the vortex structures of the propeller at the design and low rotational speeds at $Q = 100 \text{ s}^{-2}$. Compared to the low rotational speed, the design rotational speed exhibits a more complex vortex system in the wake, induced by the propeller tip and hub. In the evaluation process of full-scale self-propulsion performance, a comparison was first made between the ITTC extrapolation and full-scale self-propulsion results. The W_{TS} at thrust identity extracted from the full-scale analysis was applied to Equation (3) to compute and compare the W_n . Additionally, the differences in self-propulsion performance between the full-scale design speed and low-speed conditions were also examined.

Figure 14. Vortices visualized based on the Q-criterion ($100s^{-2}$) at the stern: (a) 14.5knots; (b) 4.0knots.

To evaluate the self-propulsion performance under both design and low-speed conditions, a comparative analysis was conducted between the ITTC extrapolation method and full-scale CFD results (Table 10 and Table 11).

The self-propulsion performance analysis referred to the stern C_p distribution according to scale and ship speed, as shown in Figure 15. The W_T showed an increasing trend in the full-scale CFD results compared to those derived from the ITTC extrapolation at both design and low-speed conditions. While W_T values obtained via ITTC extrapolation decreased with reduced speed, the full-scale CFD results maintained relatively high W_T values. This behavior is attributed to the more pronounced increase in the C_{FM} relative to the C_{FS} as speed decreases. Regarding the t , the full-scale results indicated lower values compared to ITTC extrapolation, mainly due to reduced stern pressure loss in the full-scale simulations. However, under low-speed conditions, the difference in thrust deduction between the model and full-scale was minimal. Additionally, both the η_R and η_D showed a decreasing tendency in the full-scale results compared to those extrapolated using the ITTC extrapolation method. This reduction is attributed to the increased inflow velocity to the propeller caused by the higher W_T , along with a decrease in the advance coefficient, particularly under low-speed conditions

Table 10. Comparison between ITTC-1978 and full-scale CFD (14.5knots)

	ITTC-1978 method	Full-scale (CFD)
Vs (knots)	14.5	
w_{IS}	0.352	0.375
t	0.201	0.191
η_H	1.217	1.294
η_R	1.006	0.960
η_O	0.561	0.548
η_D	0.686	0.681

Table 11. Comparison between ITTC-1978 and full-scale CFD (4.0knots)

	ITTC-1978 method	Full-scale (CFD)
Vs (knots)	4.0	
w_{IS}	0.339	0.382
t	0.184	0.184
η_H	1.234	1.321
η_R	1.022	0.970
η_O	0.536	0.519
η_D	0.676	0.665

Figure 15. C_p distribution under design and low-speed self-propulsion conditions: (a) 14.5knots (Model-scale); (b) 14.5knots (Full-scale); (c) 4.0knots (Model-scale); (d) 4.0knots (Full-scale).

To analyze the W_T under design and low-speed conditions, a comparative analysis of the W_n was conducted by substituting the W_{TS} values calculated via the ITTC method and full-scale CFD into Equation (3).

A comparative analysis of Figure 16(a) (applying W_{TS} derived via the ITTC method) and Figure 16(b) (applying W_{TS} estimated from full-scale CFD analysis) at the design speed revealed that the CFD-based W_{TS} exhibited superior agreement with the $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ obtained from full-scale CFD compared to the ITTC method. Under low-speed conditions, the accuracy of the CFD-based W_{TS} significantly improved relative to the design speed, with pronounced similarity observed within the $r/R=0.2-0.5$ radial range (Figure 16(c) and Figure 16(d)). However, differences in the $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ were observed in the $r/R=0.5-1.0$ range-the region associated with the bilge vortex-under both design and low-speed conditions. As previously noted, this highlights the need for a scaling methodology to extrapolate the position and size of the bilge vortex (a flow separation phenomenon in the three-dimensional boundary layer) to full-scale conditions.

Figure 16. Radial distribution of W_n calculated by applying W_{TS} values extracted from the ITTC method and full-scale CFD: (a) 14.5knots (ITTC method); (b) 14.5knots (Full-scale CFD); (c) 4.0knots (ITTC method); (d) 4.0knots (Full-scale CFD).

To evaluate the self-propulsion performance of a full-scale ship under low-speed conditions, CFD analyses were conducted at both the design speed (14.5 knots) and a low speed (4.0 knots), and the results were compared based on key propulsion performance indicators, as shown in Table 12. The W_{TS} were found to increase at a low speed, primarily due to a decrease in inflow velocity toward the stern. This increase in wake fraction led to an improvement in η_H , while the t showed a slight reduction because of diminished pressure losses around the stern region. Meanwhile, the η_R remained nearly constant across both speed conditions, indicating that it is less sensitive to speed variations. On the other hand, the η_O decreased under low-speed conditions, which is attributed to a reduction in the advance coefficient and an increase in torque coefficient. As a result, the η_D exhibited a moderate decline at a low speed compared to the design condition. These trends are further supported by the stern C_p distributions, which show a broader high-pressure region forward of the propeller under low-speed conditions, correlating with the observed decrease in the thrust deduction factor. Overall, these findings confirm that the CFD-based self-propulsion prediction method is capable of reliably capturing performance variations across different operating speeds, including steady low-speed conditions.

Table 12. Comparison of self-propulsion performance between the ITTC-1978 method and full-scale CFD

	ITTC-1978 method	Full-scale (CFD)
V_s (knots)	14.5 knots	4.0 knots
w_{TS}	0.375	0.382
t	0.191	0.184
η_H	1.294	1.321
η_R	0.960	0.970
η_O	0.548	0.519
η_D	0.681	0.665

5 Conclusions

In this study, full-scale resistance and POW performance were analyzed to evaluate the self-propulsion performance of the full-scale ship. By comparing the results with those obtained using the ITTC-1978 extrapolation method, the accuracy of the full-scale self-propulsion prediction was assessed. Additionally, the self-propulsion characteristics under low-speed conditions were examined in comparison to the design speed, leading to the following conclusions.

- To perform the full-scale self-propulsion analysis, the numerical methods for both model-scale and full-scale simulations were verified and validated. The model-scale resistance simulation was validated through comparison with experimental results. The validated model-scale grid was then extended to the full-scale configuration, and the GCI test confirmed convergence within 1%, demonstrating the reliability of the full-scale grid system. In addition, due to the influence of scale effects, the full-scale CR exhibited a decreasing trend compared to the model-scale results.
- The evaluation of full-scale POW performance revealed that, due to the increase in Reynolds number, K_T tends to increase while K_Q decreases compared to the model-scale. Furthermore, a comparison of POW performance between the full-scale design and low rotational speeds showed similar results regardless of the rotational speed. This indicates that the POW performance at the design rotational speed can be reliably used to extract self-propulsion factors under low-speed conditions.
- The differences in self-propulsion performance between the ITTC extrapolation method and full-scale CFD were evaluated. Contrary to the full-scale CFD results, the W_T from the ITTC-1978 method was found to increase as speed decreased. When the W_{TS} extracted from full-scale CFD was applied using wake field scaling, the resulting $W_{n(Full-scale)}$ showed good agreement with that obtained from the ITTC-1978 method.
- Under low-speed conditions, a reduction in inflow velocity and stern pressure loss led to an increase in the W_{TS} and a decrease in the t . As the effective wake fraction increased, η_H also improved. However, due to the relatively lower advance ratio at low speeds, η_o was reduced.

In this study, full-scale numerical simulations were conducted under calm water and low-speed conditions, and the flow characteristics induced by Reynolds number differences were analyzed. Based on the evaluation of full-scale resistance and POW performance, the self-propulsion characteristics were estimated, providing a foundation for future research on predicting full-scale self-propulsion performance under low-speed conditions. In future work, added resistance analysis in regular head waves under low-speed conditions will be conducted, and the required engine power will be estimated using the load variation method.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by a grant from the “Development and demonstration of data platform for AI-based safe fishing vessel design (RS-2022-KS221571)” funded by Ministry of Oceans and Fisheries, Republic of Korea, and the “Development of evaluation technology for ship’s performance in extreme environment” of the Korea Research Institute of Ships and Ocean Engineering Endowment Project, which was funded by the Ministry of Oceans and Fisheries (PES5460).

References

- [1] Ø. Buhaug, J.J. Corbett, Ø. Endresen, V. Eyring, J. Faber, S. Hanayama, D.S. Lee, D. Lee, H. Lindstad, A.Z. Markowska, A. Mjelde, D. Nelissen, J. Nilsen, C. Pålsson, J.J. Winebrake, W. Wu, and K. Yoshida. *Second IMO GHG Study 2009*. International Maritime Organization (IMO), London, UK, April 2009.
- [2] H.G. Lim, K.Y. Han, and J.W. Lee. A study on the application of EEXI to ships exempted from GHG reduction measures. *Journal of the Korean Society of Marine Engineering*, 26(4):349–357, 2023.
- [3] P. Cariou. Is slow steaming a sustainable means of reducing CO₂ emissions from container shipping *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 16(3):260–264, 2011.
- [4] J.J. Corbett, H. Wang, and J.J. Winebrake. The effectiveness and costs of speed reductions on emissions from international shipping. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 14(8):593–598, 2009.
- [5] A. Dogrul, S. Song, and Y.K. Demirel. Scale effect on ship resistance components and form factor. *Ocean Engineering*, 209:107428, 2020.
- [6] H. Yang, B.N. Kim, J. Yoo, and W.J. Kim. Wake comparison between model and full scale ships using CFD. *Journal of the Society of Naval Architects of Korea*, 47(2):150–162, 2010.
- [7] S. Gaggero, D. Villa, M. Viviani, and E. Rizzuto. Ship wake scaling and effect on propeller performances. In C. Guedes Soares and R. López Peña, editors, *Developments in Maritime Transportation and Exploitation of Sea Resources*, pages 13–21. Taylor & Francis Group, London, 2014.

- [8] I.R. Park, K.S. Kim, J.I. Kim, H.S. Seol, Y.H. Park, and J.W. Ahn. Numerical study on propeller cavitation and pressure fluctuation of model and full scale ship for a MR tanker. *Journal of the Society of Naval Architects of Korea*, 57(1):35–44, 2020.
- [9] K.-W. Kim, K.-J. Paik, J.-H. Lee, S.-S. Song, M. Atlar, and Y.K. Demirel. A study on the efficient numerical analysis for the prediction of full-scale propeller performance using CFD. *Ocean Engineering*, 240:109931, 2021.
- [10] A.M. Castro, P.M. Carrica, and F. Stern. Full scale self-propulsion computations using discretized propeller for the KRISO container ship KCS. *Computers & Fluids*, 51:35–47, 2011.
- [11] J.E. Choi, J.H. Kim, and H.G. Lee. Computational study of the scale effect on resistance and propulsion performance of VLCC. *Journal of the Society of Naval Architects of Korea*, 48(3):222–232, 2011.
- [12] I.B. Celik, U. Ghia, P.J. Roache, and C.J. Freitas. Procedure for estimation and reporting of uncertainty due to discretization in CFD applications. *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, ASME, Editorial Policy Document, 2008.
- [13] G.-H. Kim, S. Hwang, S.-H. Lee, J.-H. Lee, J. Hwangbo, K.-S. Kim, and K.-J. Paik. A numerical study on the performance of the 66k DWT bulk carrier in regular and irregular waves. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 11:1913, 2023.
- [14] ITTC – Recommended Procedures and Guidelines, 7.5–02–03–01.4. *1978 ITTC Performance Prediction Method*, Revision 02, International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC), 2011.